

Green Finance: A Study on Its Awareness among The Bank Employees of Assam

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Abstract

The changing global scenario of the 21st century calls for sustainable development Owing to the growing environmental concerns. Due to Global warming, it becomes imperative to adopt renewable and clean energy sources. This is the reason, green finance i.e. financing of investments that provide environmental benefits in the broader context of environmentally sustainable development, is important not only from the business point of view but also for environmental science. Sustainable growth requires financing; therefore Green Finance has become need of the hour. The main aim of Green Finance is to attract investment in green projects, increase return on investment on such projects and discourage polluting investments. In order to achieve non zero emission country by 2070, to expand the energy capacity not coming from fossil fuels to 500 GW by 2030 and to cut the carbon intensity of economy by 45% by 2030, green finance is very important. In this study, researcher has focused on to understand the need, benefits and various instruments of green finance and the level of awareness that the employees of the banks have on green finance to make its customer aware about the fact and the various steps taken by the banks to spread the awareness among its customers to invest in green finance related projects.

Keywords Green Finance, Sustainable Development, Bank, Employees, Investment

Introduction

The need for sustainable development is increasing in the 21st century due to the problems like ozone layer depletion, global warming, increasing pollution level and other environmental issues. Natural resources like mineral ores, fossil fuels, agricultural productivity, and the self-purification capacity of the natural environment all have their own disadvantages. Irrational consumption of resources together with irresponsible environmental pollution resulting from the entire product life cycle. This issue now –a- days gives importance to the concept of ‘green finance’.

Sustainable development: meaning- it is a development strategy which meets the needs of present generation without reducing the ability of the future generation to meet their own needs.

Green finance: meaning- financing of investment in all financial sectors and asset classes that integrate Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) considerations into the investment decisions and embed sustainability into risk management for encouraging the development of a more sustainable economy.

Aim of study

The study has been conducted with the following objectives:

1. To see the needs and benefits of Green Finance.
2. To know the various instruments available for green finance.

3. To study the awareness among the bank employees and challenges faced by them in relation to green finance in Assam.

Review of Literature

Various authors, academicians, research scholars, government and non- government agencies have conducted studies on different aspects of green finance. A few relevant literatures relating to green finance have been discussed as follows:

Jayasubramanian and Shanthi (2014), in the study, highlighted the strengths and weaknesses of green finance and also given few suggestions on it. Strengths such as promotion of technology diffusion, eco-efficient infrastructure etc., weaknesses such as lack of awareness, lack of competition etc.

Sudhalakshmi and Chinnadorai (2014) explains the concept of green finance and as per the author, green finance is very important for India to 'Go Green' as it connects with the environmental improvement through the financial perspective.

Keerthi B.S. (2013), has analysed about the challenges and opportunities of green finance in India along with the concept of creating green jobs in India.

Tasnimuddin Chowdhury et al (2013), in the study, discussed about the role of green finance in economic development and explained financing in renewable energy, green building projects etc.

Thus, the review of literature and research activities shows that many studies have been done on green finance but no study has been taken to study the green finance awareness among the bank employees of Guwahati, Assam . Therefore, this study has been undertaken.

Main Text**Importance of the study**

The world is facing unprecedented challenges caused by climate change, as a result, the financial institution are increasingly adopting a sustainability agenda. Banks are one of the primary source of funding for sustainable projects, and they have a key role to play in promoting the adoption of green finance. However, the bank employees face various challenges in promoting green finance in Assam, a state in northeastern India. Here, the researcher will discuss the challenges faced by bank employees in promoting green finance in Assam and suggest possible solutions.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data have been collected. Primary data have been collected by distributing well structured questionnaire among banks of Assam and also through interviews with the bank managers. Secondary data have been taken from websites, journals and other publications.

Sampling

Purposive random sampling technique has been adopted and 80 bank employees have been taken as samples for the study.

Tools Used Percentahe method, bar graph and pie diagram.

Analysis

By analysing the various data and information collected from various sources, the following findings have been gathered:

Need and benefits of green finance

- i. Green finance helps in the development of environmental friendly infrastructure.
- ii. Business can create value by increasing their participation in green financing and thereby attract more environmentally concerned investors and customers.
- iii. Green finance leads to the improvement of environment and helps to trade actively in the carbon market.
- iv. Investment in green projects will lead to creation of employment in India.

To provide financing of public policies which will encourage the implementation of environmental and environmental- damage mitigation or adaptation projects and initiatives.

Diagram showing the various benefits of green finance.

The various sectors where green finance can be availed of are:

Instruments of green finance in India

The following are the instruments that has been found during the study:-

Green fund

A green fund is a mutual fund which invest only in companies that focus on social consciousness or directly promote environmental responsibility. A green fund can be seen in the form of investment vehicle where companies are engaged in environmentally supportive businesses such as solar energy, wind mill, green buildings, green transport, water and waste management, and sustainable living.

Green bonds

A green bond is a type of debt security issued by an organization for the purpose of raising funds or refinancing projects that contribute towards environmental benefits. A green bond is also known as a climate bond. The way the green bond works is similar to the loan process of the banks.

Green credits

Green credits refers to the practice of banks taking into consideration not only economic benefit indicators but also environmental factors for the credit issuance process and then making appropriate loan decision.

Sustainability linked bonds

A sustainability linked bond (SLB) is a debt instrument where financial and structural factors are based on whether the issuers achieve sustainability or ESG goals within a given period of time. If the company doesn't meet those goals, there's a penalty with a higher interest to be paid by the investors.

Awareness on green finance among the bank employees.

Lack of awareness and understanding of green finance among the bank employees has been found during the study

Diagram showing the level of awareness among the bank employees.

There are many reasons for the lack of awareness like less publicity, training program, bank publications, word of mouth promotion and others for the bank employees. Among the various reason lack of training is the main issue

Diagram showing the awareness program provided to the bank employees

The various sectors where green finance can be availed of are:

Result and Discussion

Challenges faced by the bank employees:

There are various challenges faced by the bank employees in promoting green finance in Assam such as-

- i. Lack of understanding about green finance by the bank employees of Assam. They are not aware about the various products and services of green finance, which makes it difficult for the bank employees to promote green finance in Assam among its customers.
- ii. In Assam, most of the banks have limited green finance products and service offerings, which makes it difficult for the bank employees to promote these products to their clients. This lack of product and service is due to the limited demand for green finance product in the region.
- iii. Bank employees face a lack of incentives in promoting green finance in Assam. There are no financial incentives or recognition programs for bank employees who

promote green finance. This lack of incentives makes it difficult for bank employees to prioritize green finance over other products and services, leading to limited promotion of green finance.

Bank employees face limited training opportunities in green finance. Most banks in Assam do not provide adequate training on green finance products and services. This lack of training makes it difficult for the bank employees to understand and promote green finance effectively

Findings After collecting the information, the findings have been summarised as follows: The banks of Assam has the green finance instruments but the investment in the instruments are low. There is lack of knowledge regarding the benefits of making the investment in green finance instrument. Lack of efforts towards the promotional activities of the concept of green finance among its bank employees and customers as well. Promotional activities such as advertisement, bank publication and so on. The bank has easy accessibility of green finance products for their customers but because of lack of knowledge the utilisation of such facility is less. There is very limited incentives provided by the banks to the bank employees to promote the concept of green finance among its customers.

Conclusion

Green finance is the need of an hour under the vast concept of Sustainable Development. Investors who are investing in the green finance instruments are thinking beyond risk and returns, they are becoming more and more responsible towards society. Increasing awareness about environment protection and increased funding of green projects has opened a wide variety of opportunities in the area of green finance. Environmentalists, government, investors, and financial institutions should clearly define the concept of green finance. It is very important for the financial institutions of Assam to take various steps for their employees and investors such as training program, incentives and so on. Various rules and regulations should be set up so that the investors funds are properly utilised. Assam, a state in Northeast India should concentrate on protection of natural resources, efficient energy management, renewable energy generation and other ecological issues with the help of green financing. Thus, it can be concluded that green finance is the best way to achieve the various goals of the Sustainable Development.

Suggestions for the future Study A few suggestions given by the researcher after the study are as follows:-

1. Awareness and Training Programs

To address the lack of awareness and understanding of green finance, banks in Assam can provide awareness and training programs on green finance. These programs can help bank employees understand the concept of green finance and its benefits. They can also provide training on green finance products and services, including green loans, green bonds, and green funds.

2. Diversification of Product and Service Offerings

Banks in Assam can diversify their product and service offerings by introducing more green finance products and services. This diversification can help bank employees promote green finance products and services to their clients more effectively. Banks can also collaborate with other financial institutions to introduce.

3. Promotional activities

The financial institutions should take some promotional activities like advertisement in different ways, bank publications, display in banks digital boards regarding the benefits and ways to invest in the green finance instruments etc for a better knowledge and awareness of the employees and the investors as well.

4. A proper rules and regulations

The government and the financial institutions should make proper rules for the screening of the green projects and also for the utilisation of the funds raised under green finance. The funds raised should be utilised for the green projects in a judicious way.

5. Availability of incentives

The financial institutions should provide various kinds of incentives to the bank employees regarding spread of awareness among the customers. This incentives will act as a motivation for the employees to work effectively as well.

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